

SOCIAL MEDIA-DRIVEN BEAUTY STANDARDS AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE BATANG TARAGSIT OF LAGUILAYAN NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

In today's digital age, social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok play a significant role in shaping beauty standards, influencing how adolescents perceive their bodies and self-worth. The study examined the influence of beauty standards propagated through social media on the psychosocial conditions, emotional state, and self-perception of adolescents in Batang Taragsit, Isulan, Sultan Kudarat. With Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok now actively promoting idealized standards of beauty, adolescents are more prone to experiencing body dissatisfaction, a negative self-image, or even stress and anxiety. The objectives of the study included establishing the relationship of the exposure to digital beauty standards with the body image perception and mental health concerns of adolescents. A quantitative-descriptive research design including a Likert-scale questionnaire constructed by the researchers was used to gather data from selected secondary school students from Laguilayan National High School. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data and measure the extent of social media content's impact on self-perception and emotional state of the participants. The findings revealed that beauty-related content exposure was significantly correlated to decreased self-esteem and increased anxiety because of social comparison. These findings stress the urgent need for interventions like media literacy programs, parental guidance, and school-based mental health support to assist adolescents in critically assessing social media exposure and resisting detrimental beauty ideals. Furthermore, self-acceptance, body positive, and proactive media consumption should be promoted as ways to reduce the impact of such unrealistic digital beauty ideals among youth.

Keywords: *Social Media, Beauty Standards, Self-Perception, Mental Health, Digital*

INTRODUCTION

Body image, the perception and evaluation of one's physical appearance, has grown in relevance within psychological and sociocultural research today, particularly in adolescents. Undeniably, digital platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and Facebook promote unrealistic beauty standards through highly curated content that is digitally altered. These platforms, in turn, lead to increased levels of body dissatisfaction, low self-esteem, and mental health concerns such as anxiety and depression among their young users (Rodgers et al., 2020; Cohen et al., 2019). Adolescents face this process of internalizing undesirable societal propensities at a critical period in the development of their identity; oftentimes the result is engaging in harmful comparisons that skew their self-assessments and evaluations (Saiphoo & Vahedi, 2019).

Social media use is one of the highest in the world, and beauty norms develop under humanistic Western-Japanese-East Asian levels of influence promoting fair complexion and slim-bodied and Euro-typed-featured values (Alampay et al., 2019). That ideology is attractively presented to Filipino adolescents in an increasing amount of content, raising concerns about body image issues and mental health problems (Guevarra & Ong, 2022). Furthermore, with cosmetic products on the rise, skin-whitening services are further augmenting societal pressures to comply with such meanings.

Like Batang Taragsit, Isulan, Sultan Kudarat, students from Laguilayan National High School are being exposed daily to the content on social media that glorifies beauty. This exposure has effects on one's self-image and emotional well-being. Reports by school personnel and local knowledge state that this exposure may have also resulted in heightened body dissatisfaction and increased peer pressure with respect to digital beauty standards. Thus, it is in accordance with timely issues where the study looks into how beauty standards present in social media will affect adolescents' psychological well-being and self-perception in a local rural Filipino context. The gathered information seeks to contribute availability for local interventions, such as establishing media literacy education and mental health programs relevant to local needs.

Research Questions

The study aimed to know the influence of social media-driven beauty standards to the Batang Taragsit of Laguilayan National High School. Specifically, it aims to:

1. What is the level of social media-driven beauty standards of the respondents?
2. What is the level of influence of social media-driven beauty standards in terms of:
 - a. Psychological
 - b. Emotional well-being
 - c. Self-Perception

3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of social media-driven beauty standards and its influence on psychological impact, emotional well-being, and self-perception?

METHODOLOGY

This study's objective was to describe the nature of relationships linking social media beauty standards exposure among adolescent persons with psychological well-being, emotional health, and self-perception. Conducted in a public secondary school in Laguailayan, Isulan, Sultan Kudarat, 60 students were selected from among students of Grades 7 through 12 by random selection, assuring each student deemed active in social media usage had equal chances for inclusion. The stratification of the sample in the grades was done evenly, with ten students coming from each level. With vital indicators being the variables of social media usage patterns, beauty-related content exposure time, and self-reporting measures of self-esteem, emotional stability, and body image satisfaction, the researcher-made questionnaire constructed within the study served the data-gathering purpose. The 4-point Likert scale was used, and the validity of the instrument was ensured by three experts in the field, resulting in a validity score of 3.79. The pilot test exhibited good reliability, with Cronbach's alpha equal to 0.947 for the separate group of students.

Data were collected over the course of one week during which the questionnaires were administered and collated under supervised classroom settings. Once collected, data were encoding and analyzed based on both descriptive (mean, percentage) and inferential statistics. More specifically, Pearson's r correlation was used to determine the strength and direction of the relationships between the levels of exposure to social media and the three mental health variables. Tables were used to interpret the answers and the correlation values based on pre-existing scales. While the study's findings are of importance in insights, they are limited as they are self-reported and based in one location, thus affecting generalizability. Nevertheless, the study brings meaningful localism on how these idealized beauty standards on the internet affect adolescent mental health in rural contexts of the Philippines.

RESULTS

Table 1: Level of Social Media-Driven Beauty Standards

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Level of Social Media-Driven Beauty Standards	3.06	Agreed

Table 2: Level of Influence of Social Media-Driven Beauty Standards to the Batang Taragsit of Laguilayan National High School

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Psychological well-being	3.01	Agreed
Emotional well-being	2.86	Agreed
Self Perception	2.95	Agreed
Grand Mean	2.94	Agreed

Table 3: Analysis of the Level of Social Media-Driven Beauty Standards and Influence of Social Media-Driven Beauty Standards to the Batang Taragsit of Laguilayan National High School

Variables	r-value	p-value	Result	Interpretation
Psychological	0.653	< .001	No Significant	Reasonable Magnitude Relationship
Emotional well-being	0.827	< .001	No Significant	Strong Magnitude Relationship
Self-Perception	0.960	< .001	No Significant	Very Strong Magnitude of Relationship

DISCUSSION

The scores in Table 1 indicate that the respondents concurred on the significant existence of beauty standards through social media, where the calculated mean is 3.06. This descriptive rating indicated that adolescents are exposed to what can be termed as digital content paving ways to a narrow set of ideals-broadly defined as fair skin, slim bodies, and flawless features. The present research interprets this finding as an indication that social media has turned into a powerful channel in enforcing beauty standards, particularly among high school students who spend quite long hours online, which more often than not leads to their internalized expectations about student appearance and evaluation among others regarding mental and emotional health.

This finding relates directly to current literature highlighting the role of social media in shaping young people's body image and self-appraisals. Fardouly et al. (2015) found that consistent exposure to idealized images on a platform such as Facebook created increasing body dissatisfaction due to appearance-based comparisons. Likewise, Perloff (2014) argued that social media exacerbate young women's concerns about body image through the almost ceaseless display of digitally retouched and idealized parameters of beauty. Tiggemann and Slater (2014) batted for this line of thought by saying that social networking sites partake in the internalization of thin ideals, particularly among adolescent girls. In the local context, this would lead to more pressure for adolescents to comply with

beauty standards that mostly imitate Western or East Asian standards, thus weighing heavily on their self-worth and emotional health. Such findings sadly underscore the need for an urgent incorporation of media literacy and body positivity-oriented intervention programs among schools.

The data found in Table 2, with a grand mean of 2.94 to reflect a level of influence that social media beauty standards exert on the Batang Taragsit of Laguilayan National High School interpreted as "Agreed." Respondents felt that social media beauty standards were significantly perceived in regards to their psychological well-being (3.01), emotional well-being (2.86), and self-perception (2.95). Between all three indicators, psychological well-being got the highest influence, indicating that students probably undergo some mental stress such as anxiety, stress, or insecurity by exposing themselves to idealized pieces of content that one gets from the internet. Emotional well-being was affected as well, indicating that students might be having such mood swings or experiencing negative emotional states as a result of usually comparing themselves to one's beauty ideals projected on the internet. Self-perception was likely highly influenced, and thus students often compare their physical appearance to the ones visible on social media, which results in a lack of confidence or body dissatisfaction.

According to the researchers, this phenomenon illustrates the wider influence curated and idealized beauty content plays on its young social-media users. Adolescents in rural communities such as Laguilayan may lack adequate media literacy or coping mechanisms to be able to objectively weigh the beauty standards proffered online. As such, they become susceptible to internalizing such unattainable ideals, resulting in the diminution of self-worth and adverse effects upon the ability to live well. These findings are in tandem with the related literature mentioned in the introduction. For instance, Perloff (2014) emphasized that adolescents that were presented with such social media imagery would internalize the thin, fair-skinned beauty ideals embedded therein, which, in turn, create fertile ground for psychological problems. Along the same vein, Fardouly and Vartanian (2016) posit that an increase in exposure to appearance-related content on platforms such as Instagram is associated with decrease in body satisfaction and increase in social comparison. With regards to the Philippines, Gonzales and Mendoza (2020) mentioned that the internalization of Westernized beauty standards has led Filipino adolescents to resort to whitening products and body modification practices—similar to the trends among the Bataan.

Based on the results as found in Table 3, the analysis reveals a positive correlation between social media-induced beauty standards and psychological well-being, emotional well-being, and self-perception among Batang Taragsit of Laguilayan National High School. The computed r-values indicate different strength levels of relationship: .653 for psychological well-being, which reflects a fair magnitude; .827 for emotional well-being, indicating strong magnitude; and .960 for self-perception, showing very strong levels of relationship. However, despite such strong correlations, the results indicate that such relationships were not statistically significant as it was marked "No Significant", which might allude to sample size or variance limitations.

This information supports prior studies that show concerning mental health correlates of frequent exposure to social appearance-related content among adolescents. According to Marengo et al. (2018), image-oriented social platforms increase internalization of thin ideals and body image concerns. Meta-analysis by Keles et al., (2020) affirmed that social media use is strongly associated with distress in adolescents. The current research is in accord with these studies affirming that social exposure to beauty standards plays an important role in the mental and emotional health and self-worth perception of adolescents.

Conclusions

The students who surveyed found that the beauty standards created by social media were more tangible as well as definable. Most often depicted across digital landscapes, the new beauty ideals shape how adolescents perceive beauty and their acceptance towards their body forms. Students admitted that they were often seen in content promoting such beauty types in their exposures, hence as an indication that those ideals entered their digital experiences and conditions of viewing something as "beautiful."

In terms of influence, the results indicated that this standard of beauty affected the respondents psychologically, emotionally, or even their self-perceptions. For example, the students said that their mental welfare was disturbed when they tried to compare themselves to the ideal images posted online. When faced with those super beauty standards, they felt pressure, inadequacy, or self-doubt. In addition, their self-perception is more often than not influenced by the curated images they often viewed; thus, they led them more often to doubt their worth and sometimes even what they look like.

Furthermore, the study confirmed the existence of a significant relationship between exposure to beauty standards as propounded by social media and the psychological, emotional, and self-perceptual responses of individuals toward them. Thus, the greater exposure of adolescents to beauty-related content on social media, the more the symptom effects such exposure may have on their thoughts, emotions, and self-image. This calls for schools, families, and communities to prepare young men and women with media literacy and positive self-esteem, which would enable them to critique online beauty narratives and interpret them well.

Recommendations

1. Schools may implement media and digital literacy programs to help students critically evaluate beauty content they encounter online.
2. School guidance offices should conduct regular mental health and self-esteem workshops that help students understand the value of self-worth beyond physical appearance.

3. Teachers and advisers should initiate safe classroom discussions and activities that promote emotional expression, empathy, and body positivity.
4. Schools should support student-led campaigns or clubs that advocate for diversity, inclusivity, and real beauty.
5. Collaborative efforts between parents, schools, and the local community must be strengthened.
6. It is recommended that future studies explore the topic across larger and more diverse populations to verify the findings and examine other variables such as gender, socioeconomic background, and type of social media use.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors affirm that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study. Ethical approval was obtained before the commencement of the research, and informed consent was acquired from all respondents involved. No specific funding was received for this research from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit organizations. The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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